

A Simple and Rapid Spectrophotometric Method to Estimate Glutaraldehyde

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Glutaraldehyde (GA), though is a cytotoxic agent, has been used extensively for crosslinking synthetic and natural materials¹. In order to monitor the release of GA from crosslinked materials, a simple, rapid and sensitive method is needed. Over these years, several methods varying from chromatographic to spectrophotometric methods have been emerged². Recently, the demerits of these methods have been reported³. The serious drawback of these methods, particularly the spectrophotometric methods, are the unstable nature of the solutions and the fading of colour within a short period of time. This communication discusses a simple spectrophotometric method involving the reaction between GA and *o*-toluidine.

Results and Discussion

o-Toluidine has commonly been used for the estimation of glucose in biological fluids particularly in blood⁴. The reaction involves the coupling of NH₂ group of *o*-toluidine with the aldehyde group of the glucose in acid medium under elevated temperature to form a Schiff's base having absorption at 620 nm. The purple coloured Schiff's base formed has strong absorption around 560 nm. Beyond 540 nm, the absorption rapidly enhances. *o*-Toluidine does not have any absorption in this region and that 560 nm can be used for monitoring the reaction between *o*-toluidine and GA and thereby for the estimation of GA.

Recently Lynn *et al.*³ have reported a spectrophotometric method for the estimation of GA. The method though sensitive uses 253 and 300 nm for monitoring the reaction and the subsequent estimation of GA. It may be relevant to point out that most of the synthetic polymers contain aromatic additives and these components could also leach along with GA from the crosslinked polymer matrices to the contacting fluids. In that case the estimation of GA using the method of Lynn *et al.*³ would be erroneous considering the fact that most of the aromatic additives have absorption at 253 nm. A wavelength preferably in the visible region seems to be ideal for the estimation of GA. We considered this aspect in the development of the present method.

Unlike in other reported methods, the solution is stable

and it can be stored for several days. The notable advantage of the method is the lack of any interference from *o*-toluidine at 560 nm. Therefore excess of *o*-toluidine can be added to ensure complete reaction of GA in a given solution. It may be mentioned that most of the commonly used polymer additives do not have absorption at 560 nm. The reported method is sensitive and the detection limit is $12 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of GA. The reaction occurs at room temperature which is another interesting feature of the method compared to other published procedures. The method is simple, rapid and sensitive and could routinely be used for the estimation of GA as well as other aldehydes commonly used as crosslinking agents.

Experimental

Glutaraldehyde (25% solution) and *o*-toluidine (both from Sigma) were used. All other reagents were of analytical grade (E. Merck).

To a mixture of glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and methanol (9 ml) were added *o*-toluidine (50 μl) and GA solution (25 μl). The colour of the solution turned instantaneously to purple indication the reaction.

A Hitachi 220 spectrophotometer was used.

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